

SOCIAL LIGHTING FOR QUALITY OF LIFE IN PUBLIC SPACE

POLICY BRIEF

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CREDITS

This policy is part of an outreach research developed in the framework of ENLIGHTENme. It has been authored by Don Slater, Elettra Bordonaro (London School of Economics) and Joanne Entwistle (King's College London)

HIGHLIGHTS

- **'Good lighting' supports the quality of life** of diverse users of urban public spaces. Good lighting design is not a technical specialism that aims to comply with uniform standards; it is a creative response to the varied and sometimes conflicting needs and concerns of citizens.
- Lighting provision needs to **be integrated within multidisciplinary teams** and policy-making processes oriented to pooling knowledge and planning to support urban demographics that share common public spaces.
- 'Social lighting' of urban public spaces requires both **social research and community engagement** in order to develop rich and reliable understandings of the needs and concerns of diverse citizens. This means understanding their social practices: what they are trying to do in the city.
- Good social lighting needs to be **adaptive, iterative, responsive**: rather than seeing lighting as static light points, fixed and only maintained for decades, lighting should be seen as an ongoing process of supporting the changing quality of life needs of a population.

AIM

This policy brief provides an overview of a strategic approach to 'social lighting' – ensuring that public lighting supports the quality of life of diverse citizens by integrating city lighting design within a holistic strategy for public space provision. The aim is to move lighting from a technical specialism to an integral part of evidence-based urban design and planning. The focus of this policy brief is on local lighting design and installation (projects, neighbourhoods and districts) rather than city wide policy or masterplanning: how can cities ensure that actual lighting implementations effectively address diverse citizen needs and concerns?

BACKGROUND

City lighting policy and design tends to be treated as a technical specialism, primarily concerned to address safety, security and transport issues, with clear cost constraints, and ensure compliance with national and regional standards and regulations. It is sometimes extended to city marketing, tourism and place-making expertise concern.

Though technical and marketing expertise are clearly crucial to good lighting, neither specialism on its own can connect lighting knowledgeably to the diverse needs and concerns of the many different types of users (or potential users) of urban public space, or integrate lighting within wider city policies for either urban development or the needs of specific demographics (eg, gender safety, ethnic inclusion or active ageing). Moreover, isolating public space lighting provision as a specialism splits it off from urban design work, often adding lighting as an afterthought rather than including it in the conceptualisation and planning of urban spaces: the result is often missed opportunities or even counterproductive interventions.

At the same time, public lighting technologies – including both LED, luminaires and control systems – have been going through their biggest technological revolution since Edison. Whereas public space lighting up to now has meant massive city investment in fixed specification light points that might have to last 30 years into the future, lighting and control technologies are now increasingly dynamic, responsive, 'smart' and controllable. Cities can make use of the ability to respond to different needs in different places and times through control of dimming schedules, motion sensors, positioning and even colour temperature. This should allow closer connection between technical and social lighting.

Cities need to rethink what they mean by 'good lighting', equating it with supporting the quality of life of diverse citizens rather than compliance with standards and simply ensuring safety and security.

RECOMMENDATIONS

'Good lighting' for urban public spaces is lighting that supports the quality of life of diverse users. A strategic approach to public lighting is one that produces rich knowledge of users' needs and concerns, integrates this knowledge with all relevant city expertise, uses lighting within a broader urban design and public service response to citizen needs and concerns and engages widely with community constituents throughout a long term process of developing public space, from baseline research through post-implementation monitoring and adaptation.

Research and engagement for social lighting

Urban communities are diverse and have not only different but often conflicting public space needs. The quality of life of an older resident may depend on brighter, bluer and more uniform lighting of paths to shopping precincts, whereas a teenager's lifestyle may depend on pockets of darkness that afford public privacy for socialising; similarly ethnic differences in aesthetic tastes and the very meaning of public space or gender differences in perceptions of safety need to be engaged and articulated. Standards and regulations often act to obscure or ignore differences that need to be addressed through design.

Cities need to understand and articulate the diverse social bases of quality of life – the needs and concerns of users – in order to generate effective lighting. This requires both social research and community engagement. One-off consultations or surveys do not generate reliable data and often push design in the wrong directions.

Focus on social practices

Supporting quality of life means supporting people in using public spaces to do what they want to do, and removing barriers to their desired activities, whether shopping, socialising, exercising, getting to work or home. Strategic social lighting approaches therefore focus on social practices rather than static lighting 'points': what are people trying to do, and how can lighting, as part of urban design, help them to do it. Often the best way to conceptualize good supportive lighting is in terms of paths or journeys, rather than points or places, focusing on the role of lighting from the start to finish of an activity.

Multidisciplinary Teamwork and strategic integration

Lighting is not simply more than a specialist engineering matter – it connects to multiple aspects of social life in a city, often unexpected but crucial factors. Therefore lighting needs to be integrated organizationally within city planning and design. For example, dealing with the public space needs of physically active older people may involve integrating expertise around policing and security, social care and elderly services, transport and mobility, community centre, design and placement of street furniture and amenities such as benches and water fountains.

Lighting needs to be 'mainstreamed' within urban design and within city initiatives or policies for specific demographics such as active ageing or older people or gender equality and safety. Teams that draw together city expertise ensures that lighting is part of wider initiatives and expertise.

Responsive and iterative lighting design

New technology and new urban design thinking have moved on from the days of uniform, static and long-term lighting solutions in which tens of thousands of lighting points would be installed to last for decades, untouched except for minimal maintenance.

- Lighting can now be far more responsive or 'smart': eg, dimming schedules can be used to 'zone' spaces for different users and uses at different times of the day, week or season;
- Lighting design can be regarded as adaptive and iterative rather than set in stone: it can and should involve post-implementation research and assessment, experimentation, monitoring for new users and uses of a public space.

